

Predicting an Adequate Ratio of Unmanned Vehicles per Operator using a System with a Mission Definition Language

M. O. Rodas, C. X. Szatkowski and M. C. Veronda

Abstract—The Department of Defense’s future vision for Network Centric Operations (NCO) will increase combat power by networking relevant entities across the battlefield. This will result in highly complex mission scenarios in which the operator’s workload will be easily overloaded if the system is not designed to support the mission requirements. New technologies for these complex command and control environments are currently being developed. Evaluating the adequacy of a particular technology for specific mission requirements is critical for military decision makers. This paper will introduce a new approach to model operator and system performance.

Index Terms — Unmanned Vehicles, Supervisory Control, Operator Capacity, Decision Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Defense’s future vision for Network Centric Operations (NCO) is intended to increase combat control by networking relevant entities across a battlefield [1]. This new vision implies large amounts of information sharing and collaboration across different entities. An example of a futuristic NCO scenario is one in which a group of heterogeneous Unmanned Vehicles (UVs) are supervised by a single operator using NCO technology. In this type of complex command and control (C2) scenario, UV operators will be subjected to vast amounts of information as compared to today’s command and control scenarios. Therefore, this vision brings with it a new problem that must be addressed: How to maintain an adequate workload to avoid information overload and resulting loss of situation awareness. Currently, C2 technologies that allow the operator to control multiple UVs in a NCO scenario are rapidly increasing. The development of these new C2 technologies generates the tendency to exponentially increase the ratio of UVs to operators. However, if systems are inadequately designed or are used beyond their design capabilities, they will not adequately control for increased workload, which in turn will cause the operator to become overloaded and lose situation awareness.

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It is critical that military decision makers develop predictive models of human and system performance to evaluate the adequacy of a system’s design to satisfy specific mission requirements.

II. BACKGROUND

Mental workload is a limiting factor in deciding how many UVs an operator can control or supervise. In the case of one operator supervising multiple vehicles, the operator’s workload is measured by the effort required to supervise each vehicle and the overall task. The effort required to supervise an individual UV in a team depends on the efficiency of the system to reduce workload and increase situation awareness. Moreover, workload also depends on the complexity of the mission scenario. Some of the characteristics of a complex mission scenario as defined by military standards include: mission time constraints, precision constraints, repeatability in tasks (i.e., navigation, manipulations, etc.), level of collaboration required, concurrence and synchronization of events and behaviors, resource management (i.e., power, bandwidth, ammunition), rules of engagement, adversaries, and knowledge requirements [2]. The degree to which these characteristics are required also define workload. Consequently, if the system is not designed to achieve specific types of requirements, then when it is tested for those requirements the system may not perform them adequately.

Previous attempts to model operator capacity were developed to display temporal constraints associated with the system. The complexity of these measures progressed from measuring operator capacity in homogenous UVs controlled by one operator [3-7], to scenarios in which teams of heterogeneous UVs are supervised by one operator [8]. The first equation developed to predict operator capacity in homogenous UVs suggested that the operator capacity is a function of the Neglect Time (NT), or the time the UV operates independently, and Interaction Time (IT), or the time the operator is busy interacting, monitoring, and making decisions with the system [3]. Critics of this method suggested that the equation lacked two critical considerations: 1) the importance of including Wait Times (WTs) caused by human-vehicle interaction, and 2) how to link this equation to measure effective performance [6]. Hence, WTs were added to the equation to account for the times the UV has to perform in a degraded state because the operator is not able to attend to it or is not aware of a new incoming event. Three WTs were identified: Wait Times due to Interaction (WTI), Wait Times

due to Loss of Situation Awareness (WTSA), and Wait Times due to Queue (WTQ).

Using a discrete event simulation, a research study attempted to create a link to performance by using a proxy to measure workload and situation awareness. In this model, the researcher intended to model heterogeneity in UV systems in order to evaluate the system’s design [8]. The human was modeled as a server attending to vehicle-generated tasks – both exogenous and endogenous tasks – as defined by their arrival and service processes. The concept of utilization was introduced as a proxy for measuring mental workload. Utilization Time (UT) refers to the percentage of time the operator is busy. The concept of WTSA was used as a proxy to measure Situation Awareness. The UT and WTSA measures were computed as a type of aggregate effect of inefficiencies in information processing rather than being computed as individual measures of workload and situation awareness. The author of this model suggested that many other sources of cognitive inefficiencies, besides these two proxies, are manifested through cognitive delays. He emphasized that measures of UT and WTSA are extremely critical to determine supervisory performance and suggested that better methodologies to measure these variables need to be developed.

III. PROJECT GOALS

This study aims to develop a model of operator capacity in a complex mission scenario that converges all previous research in the area to create a more comprehensive model of operator capacity. This comprehensive model is intended to fill in the gaps of current research by introducing new variables and relationships to previous models. The model will be constructed in a way so prior knowledge about the relationship between variables will serve to better predict missing data, such as workload and situation awareness. Moreover, the model will be structured in a way that will make it easy to determine which areas in the system design need improvement. The ultimate goal of this study is to develop a decision-making tool that will serve to evaluate and determine the effectiveness and limitations of a particular NCO technology in a complex mission scenario.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Approach

The approach taken by this research study was to model the decision-making process required to decide whether to increase a particular team size. This approach was taken in order to present decision makers with a decision-support tool that will ensure that knowledgeable decisions are made in regards to the adequacy of a given team size with a particular NCO technology. Modeling the decision-making process, as opposed to the environment, allows for more knowledgeable decisions because not only are the most important factors in the decision taken into account, but optimization of the recommended decision’s outcome is also possible. This approach provides adequate information to the user to make a decision. And while the model is based on answering this particular question, the nature of the situation is manifested in

the model, thus allowing users to draw more conclusions than only the adequacy of the team size.

B. Decision Network

A decision network was developed to model the decision-making process required to decide whether to increase a given team size with the selected NCO technology. Netica Bayesian Belief Network (BBN) Software [9] was used to develop a decision network that incorporates quantitative and qualitative information about the model. This software was chosen mainly because it can accommodate missing or incomplete data. Using a BBN allows researchers to compute unobservable variables (i.e., missing data) based on measures that are observed (i.e., prior knowledge).

A decision network consists of nature, decision, and utility nodes. Nature nodes represent variables over which the decision maker has no control (see yellow nodes in Fig. 1). Decision nodes represent variables over which the decision maker can make a decision (see blue nodes in Fig. 1). Utility nodes represent a measure of value, or the decision maker’s preferences for the states of the variables in the model (see pink nodes in Fig. 1). In this network, the outcome of a decision node is maximized by finding a configuration of the various states of the sets of variables that maximize the values of the utility node. Therefore, based on a series of requirements, or utility values, a decision network provides the user with the correct decision. Additionally, the arrows in the model represent reasoning relationships and are detailed in the conditional probability tables (CPTs) of the nature and utility nodes. In the CPT, the distribution of each node will be determined *a priori* based on the relationships specified in each conditional probability table.

Fig. 1. Decision network representing the decision process involved in deciding whether to increase a particular team size. Notice that this picture displays the model with no data. When data are introduced into the model, the system provides the user with a recommended course of action that will be displayed as a percentage (i.e., Yes 90%).

C. Model Description

In this model, the human operator is responsible for supervising a team of heterogeneous UVs defending an oil platform from potential enemies. The model is based on three major areas of relevance for the decision to increase the team size: system performance, operator performance, and cognitive workload (See Fig. 1). These areas of relevance are

represented in the model as sub-models; each of them contains one or more decision nodes that correspond to the decisions that must be made by the operator in each area to ensure that they are working adequately. The order in which the decision nodes have been organized represents the way in which decisions should be made (see blue nodes on Fig. 1). The model represents a sequence of decisions in which later decisions depend on the results of earlier ones. In this model, the last decision is shown at the end of the sequence. The last decision determines whether the team size should be increased.

The first sub-model, system performance, includes three decision nodes with the followings decisions: 1) Is the interface effective? 2) Does the system have an adequate level of automation? 3) Are the system algorithms efficient for the task? These three decisions were included in this sub-model because they represent areas that are important to ensure good system performance. Some of the utility nodes for each of these decision nodes were identified from the literature, while some others were included to ensure that specific mission requirements are satisfied. For example, if the system has good interface usability, the situation awareness of the operator will be high. Moreover, if the situation awareness is high, the system's automation level must be somehow effective to avoid loss of situation awareness and/or complacency. Then, to ensure that the mission requirements are satisfied, the algorithms used must be working efficiently toward achieving the mission goal. This efficiency is measured by the number of times the operator reassigns a mission that was previously assigned by the system, with a lower number signaling higher efficiency. Note that algorithm efficiency is defined in this model only as a result of the operator's perceived trustworthiness of the system. If the system is not perceived as trustworthy, then the operator will tend to override the system frequently and the algorithm efficiency will be low.

The second sub-model, operator performance, needs to ensure that the operator performs effectively with the system being evaluated, as more UVs are introduced to the team, and the mission scenario becomes more complex. Since this is a supervisory control environment, operator performance is defined in terms of the operator's decision making. There are two decisions (decision nodes) that are important to evaluate whether the operator's performance is adequate for the task: 1) Is the operator's task management strategy efficient? 2) Is the operator's decision making efficient? The first decision is necessary to evaluate whether operators will efficiently prioritize different tasks that arrive simultaneously. The second decision is necessary to evaluate whether the operator will successfully achieve the goals of the mission (i.e., protecting the asset from enemy attack). Together these two decisions summarize what is important to ensure a satisfactory operator performance. Please note that by measuring task management efficiency, an attention inefficiency component is included in this model.

Finally, the last sub-model, cognitive workload, includes the final decision node: "Increase Team?" For this decision, it is important to ensure that operators are not overloaded, but instead their workload is adequate to successfully complete the mission scenario. This final decision node is the end of a

sequence of decisions and therefore it depends on the outcomes of the previous decisions made in the system performance and operator performance sub-models. Hence, in order to avoid cognitive overload, not only does the system have to efficiently perform in the mission scenario, but the operator also has to perform efficiently to ensure that tasks are adequately managed and do not overload the operator. The cognitive workload and operator performance sub-models are strongly associated. If cognitive workload is too high, then the operator performance will be low. Therefore, the more inadequate management and tactical decisions operators make, the higher their workload will be.

System performance, operator performance, and cognitive workload are the foundation of this model. Most of the knowledge about the model relationships between variables was acquired from a literature review. Variables such as "Information Overload" and "System Interruption" were included to emphasize the need to evaluate these aspects of the usability of the system (see Fig. 1) in complex supervisory control tasks. These variables are relevant because they contribute to design interfaces, especially in the supervisory control environment in which large amounts of information, and large event queues can result in information overload and frequent system interruptions.

D. Simulation

In order to test the validity of the model's outcome, a simulation tool will be used. A simulator will provide the data required to feed the model variables, and then the model results will be compared to the experimental trials. Since there is no simulation available that portrays all the complexities of a futuristic mission scenario, the Research Environment for Supervisory Control of Heterogeneous Unmanned Vehicles (RESCHU) developed by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) was acquired and later modified for use in this study. The RESCHU simulator [8] was developed to test supervisory control tasks such as surveillance and identification. This simulation was modified for this study to include the following requirements: 1) a complex mission scenario with an asset to protect and multiple simultaneous enemies to attack, 2) a highly automated system such as mission definition language (MDL) and 3) a highly heterogeneous team that is made of at least three different types of UVs. The new version of the simulation is called RESCHU SP.

It is important to mention that the MDL was selected as an example of a NCO technology that allows one operator to supervise multiple UVs. In this study, the MDL chosen is the Collaborative Sensing Language (CSL) developed at the University of California, Berkeley. The CSL [10] is a high-level feedback control language for mobile sensor networks of UAVs. This system allows an operator to concentrate on high-level decisions, while the system takes care of low-level decisions, like choosing which UV to send for a particular type of task. A framework for the CSL was designed to integrate this technology into the complex mission scenario portrayed by the RESCHU SP simulator. The CSL version displayed in this simulation is only intended to illustrate one

way to portray how this technology may work in more complex mission scenarios and with supervisory control of heterogeneous UVs (See Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. RESCHU SP simulator displays a mission scenario with a team size of nine UVs (blue icons in the map), three potential enemies (dark yellow icons in the map), and one identified enemy (red numbered icon in the map). The CSL tab shows missions that are currently active and other missions that are not yet submitted.

E. Experimental Trials

Experimental trials will be conducted online. The online trial will include: a background and exit survey, a tutorial, a trial game, and one of a set of possible experimental conditions. UV operators from the U.S. Navy, Army, and Air Force will be invited to participate in this study. In addition, non-UV operators will be recruited from the Naval Postgraduate School (NPS) to participate in the study. The online simulation will be only accessible to participants with a Department of Defense Common Access Card (CAC). The study design will be a between subject design with three conditions: high team size (9 UVs), medium team size (7 UVs), and low team size (5 UVs). The data collected from the experimental trials will not only be used to feed the model, but will also be used to develop workload and situational awareness curves that will help determine a baseline from which performance starts to decline for these two measures. Later, this information will be incorporated into the model as part of the operator capacity requirements.

V. ONGOING WORK

The simulation and the simulation's tutorial were modified based on the results of a pilot test completed at the NPS. The simulation is currently ready to start collecting data online; however, paperwork still has to be processed in order to put the simulation on a secure site. It is expected that by January 25, 2011 experimental trials will begin.

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